

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of web quality on E-Loyalty through E-Trust and E-Satisfaction on the shopee marketplace

Rifka Zahra ^{1,*}, Andi Wijayanto ² and Sari Listyorini ²

¹ Master of Business Administration, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia.

² Department of Business Administration, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(02), 1838–1850

Publication history: Received on 12 July 2024; revised on 19 August 2024; accepted on 21 August 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.2.2520>

Abstract

This study aims to prove and analyze web quality on e-loyalty through e-trust and e-satisfaction on the shopee marketplace. The number of samples was 97 Shopee customers using a purposive sampling approach. Data collection techniques are questionnaires with a Likert scale of 1-5 points. Data analysis using Smart PLS. The conclusion of this study is that website quality has a positive and significant effect on e-loyalty, website quality has positive and significant effect on e-trust, the effect of website quality on e-satisfaction is positive and significant, the effect of e-trust on e-loyalty is negative and insignificant, the effect of e-trust on e-satisfaction is positive and significant, the effect of e-satisfaction on e-loyalty is positive and significant, E-trust is insignificant mediate the effect of web quality on e-loyalty, while E-satisfaction is mediate positively and significantly the effect of web quality on e-loyalty.

Keywords: E-loyalty; Web Quality; E-trust; E-satisfaction; Shopee Customer

1. Introduction

The internet has changed the traditional way of purchasing goods and services, users are no longer limited by time and geographical factors, they can actively purchase products and goods regardless of time and location factors (1). Electronic commerce (e-commerce) is an activity to buy or sell products, or to exchange valuable data, through an online platform (2).

In Indonesia, e-commerce that implements the C2C business concept, one of which is Shopee (3). Shopee in Indonesia was officially introduced in Indonesia in December 2015 under the auspices of PT Shopee International Indonesia. Since its launch, Shopee Indonesia has experienced very rapid development, even until October 2017 the application has been downloaded by more than 25 million users (3). E-loyalty can be defined as a consumer's intention to revisit an online store on a particular e-commerce website, to repurchase their products (4). Therefore, e-loyalty can be seen as a specific form of psychological attachment to a particular e-commerce (5). E-satisfaction is the result of the overall experience and satisfaction related to the e-commerce site (1).

Shopee in Indonesia was officially introduced in Indonesia in December 2015 under the auspices of PT Shopee International Indonesia. Since its launch, Shopee Indonesia has experienced very rapid development, even until October 2017 the application has been downloaded by more than 25 million users (3). Shopee in 2021-2023 is a type of e-commerce service that has a ranking of 1 on average visiting its website. From 2021-2023, Shopee visitors could increase again. The increase was not significant from 2021-2023.

E-trust or customer trust plays an important role in increasing customer satisfaction for online shopping (1). They also proved that trust in e-commerce can be gained when people know that the store owner cannot cheat or defraud, the

* Corresponding author: Rifka Zahra

store is safe to transact and the website is optimized to be friendly and easy to use. If consumers feel that the website is of high quality, they tend to have high trust in the competence, integrity and benevolence of the web retailer (6). This study aims to analyze the effect of web quality on e-loyalty through e-trust and e-satisfaction on the Shopee marketplace.

2. Literature Review

Consumer purchasing behaviour refers to the process by which individuals search for, select, purchase, use, and dispose of goods and services, to satisfy their needs and wants (7). Providing quality service is considered an important strategy for success in today's competitive environment. Perceived service quality is the result of comparing perceptions and reality about the performance offered by the service provider (8). Previous findings indicate the need to understand how e-loyalty is developed, e-satisfaction, and e-trust are key factors to build e-loyalty. These factors have direct and indirect effects on loyalty. That is, each factor affects e-loyalty individually and then impacts other factors that have a direct effect on e-loyalty itself (9).

2.1. E-loyalty

The materials and methods should be typed in Cambria with font size 10 and justify alignment. Author can select Normal style setting from Styles of this template. The simplest way is to replace (copy-paste) the content with your own material. Method and analysis which is performed in your research work should be written in this section. A simple strategy to follow is to use keywords from your title in first few sentences.

E-loyalty can be defined as a consumer's intention to revisit a particular e-tailer's website, to repurchase their products (4). The concept of e-loyalty extends the traditional concept of loyalty to online consumer behavior (10) defines e-loyalty as the intention to revisit a website or make transactions from it in the future.

The importance of e-loyalty in a company is that loyal customers not only increase sales and business profits but also enable it to reduce costs associated with attracting new customers (9). Observed that creating and maintaining a loyal customer base is critical because these companies earn most of their revenue from third parties, such as partners and advertisers (11). E-loyalty is measured by the following indicators: repurchasing a product, giving recommendations to other consumers; and revisiting the website (2).

2.2. E-satisfaction

E-Satisfaction can be seen as the customer's overall assessment that a product or service provides a pleasant level of consumption-related fulfilment, it can also be defined as the result of a comparison between what customers expect about the service provided by the service provider and what customers receive in reality (12). The better the quality of electronic services provided, the more satisfied customers they will have (13).

Showed that there are several e-satisfaction factors, namely website design, reliability or fulfilment, customer service, and security. In terms of the website, it is described as the presentation and ability of the site considering its usability, user friendliness, aesthetic design, interactivity, layout, navigation, checkout, search capabilities and information quality (11).

To measure e-satisfaction, it can be seen from the customer's attitude towards an e-commerce. Satisfied customers will engage in repeat purchasing behaviour, customers show the level of joy they feel when their purchasing and post-purchase experiences exceed their expectations(14). The satisfaction felt by someone when their desires, needs, or expectations are fulfilled (11).

E-satisfaction is measured by the following indicators: Consumers are happy with the services on the website; Consumers are satisfied with the services of this website; Consumers are happy to make purchases on this website; Consumers are satisfied with their purchasing decisions on this website (15, 16).

2.3. E-Trust

E-trust affects customers' perceptions of control over their online transactions, online trust has been identified as one of the main antecedents of e-loyalty, to gain customer loyalty, you must first gain their trust (17) trust is also defined as the perception of confidence that individuals have in the reliability and integrity of their exchange partners and is related to individual beliefs about their integrity, policies, abilities, and credibility (18).

E-trust is measured through a three-indicator scale, namely: (1) I believe that Internet shopping is a safe activity; (2) E-commerce sites are trustworthy; (3) e-commerce gives the impression that they will keep their commitments (19). Trust has been established as an important concept for online shopping because it can help build long-term relationships between customers and companies (20).

2.4. Web Quality

Website quality is defined as the perception of how users evaluate a website for its features that meet their needs stated that a website is not only an information system, but also an interface with vendors (1).

Website quality can also be conceptualized as a consumer's assessment of the overall superiority and suitability of a site for use in assisting the task or purpose of making an online purchase, therefore, website quality should be a critical business concern, especially in an e-commerce perspective, because the low percentage of website visitors with buyers from the site is relevant to each other (1).

The dimensions of web quality have been identified by previous researchers in several categories, namely: information, security, ease of use, satisfaction, and service quality (8). Web quality is measured by the following indicators: information, security, ease of use, satisfaction, service quality (8).

2.5. Hypothesis

2.5.1. *The influence of website quality on e-loyalty*

Revealed the dimensions of website quality that affect e-loyalty, such as design, content, and structure (21). The impact of website quality on consumer behaviour, especially on e-loyalty, has received little attention in the literature (22). Showed that website design plays an important role in attracting and retaining customers. The direct effect of website design on e-loyalty and confirmed that an easy-to-use interface that suits user needs, provides the necessary information (23), will be rewarded with increased loyalty if the service quality of the website is attractive to customers (17), the chances of developing a positive assessment of the site will be high (11).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 1 as follows:

H1 : Website quality has a positive effect on e-loyalty;

2.5.2. *The influence of web quality on e-trust*

E-trust can be seen as a guarantee of security, reputation, fulfilment (e.g. willingness to customize), presentation (e.g. web quality), technology and interaction (e.g. e-forms) (12). There are 4 dimensions of web quality determinants, one of which is directly related to e-trust, namely website security. Website security is considered one of the main concerns in the context of e-shopping (12). In addition, e-trust can be described by the ability of a website to conduct online transactions to improve its performance and level of trust (24).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 2 as follows:

H2 : Website quality has a positive effect on e-trust;

2.5.3. *The influence of web quality on e-trust*

A website that has advantages will increase user readiness and satisfaction to use it (21). Proved that there are three factors that have a positive effect on electronic satisfaction, namely relevant information, transactional capacity, and response time (21). Four factors that determine the quality of a website, including: system, information, service, and design and their impact on electronic satisfaction (21). The perceived quality of the website is a determinant of customer satisfaction (21).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 3 as follows:

H3 : Website quality has a positive effect on e-satisfaction;

2.5.4. The influence of e-trust on e-loyalty

E-trust has been identified as one of the main antecedents of e-loyalty, to gain customer loyalty, you must first gain their trust (17). There are several dimensions of how e-trust can increase e-loyalty, an important dimension is integrity which is the perception that the trusted party will keep promises, be honest, and adhere to accepted rules of behavior, therefore, generating e-trust depends on the ability of the trusted party to deliver on promises made and meet customer expectations (11). An equally important dimension is the site's ability to accurately display and describe products so that customers receive what they think they ordered.

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 4 as follows:

H4 : E-trust has a positive effect on e-loyalty;

2.5.5. The influence of e-trust on e-satisfaction

Consumer trust always plays an important role in maintaining business relationships, especially in demanding e-commerce business consumers to pay before receiving orders, even though consumers cannot see or touch the real product offered except through images (25). In a study conducted by Azli and Ghane (9), that e-trust has a direct and positive effect on e-satisfaction. When the level of customer trust in electronics increases, customer satisfaction with electronics also increases. This is because customers feel more confident and safe in transacting online, thus contributing to a positive online shopping experience (26).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 5 as follows:

H5 : E-Trust has a positive effect on e-satisfaction;

2.5.6. The influence of e-satisfaction on e-loyalty

Satisfaction has been shown to be positively related to loyalty and this effect also occurs in the online environment. The influence of satisfaction on loyalty is stronger online than offline. Satisfied customers tend to have higher service usage, have stronger repurchase intentions, and are more likely to recommend products or services to their acquaintances than those who are dissatisfied (9). Satisfying customer experiences with a particular e-commerce are expected to increase their desire to make more online purchases from that e-commerce (loyalty) (9).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 6 as follows:

H6 : E-satisfaction has a positive effect on e-loyalty;

2.5.7. The mediating role of e-trust in the influence of web quality on e-loyalty

Website quality has been considered as a determinant factor that increases e-trust, it is expected that website quality can affect e-trust (17). Users will form their perception of quality depending on the characteristics of the website: information, navigation structure and graphic design (27). Thus, through the mediation of web quality e-trust has a direct positive effect on e-loyalty (2). When the level of customer trust in electronics increases, customer satisfaction with electronics also increases. This is because customers feel more confident and safe in transacting online, thus contributing to a positive online shopping experience (26).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 7 as follows:

H7 : Web quality influences e-loyalty through e-trust;

2.5.8. The mediating role of e-satisfaction in the influence of web quality on e-loyalty

Website is the first communication channel for customers and companies or organizations in e-business (28). Website plays a major role in customer loyalty if it can meet customer needs when first accessed. Conducted a study with the aim of integrating the e-loyalty development process model (28). The second most intense relationship is between security and privacy and trust, the greater the guarantee of security and protection of personal data, the more consumer trust in the platform. They concluded that website design has a significant effect on e-satisfaction and a significant effect on the e-loyalty development process. They used the structural equation model method in this analysis (28).

Based on the above in the research hypothesis 8 as follows:

H8 : Web quality influences e-loyalty through e-satisfaction;

Figure 1 Research Framework

3. Research Methods

This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method that uses primary data from questionnaires. The type of research used is explanatory research. Researchers use secondary data from books, scientific journals, and certain official websites. The population of this study is users of the Shopee application in the Pekanbaru area. A total of 97 samples using a purposive sampling approach. Questions using a Likert scale of 1-5. This study uses data analysis with the structural equation modelling (SEM) method using Partial Least Squares (PLS).

4. Research Result

The majority in this study were female gender as much as 74%. More ages 19-29 years as much as 77%. More jobs are private employees as much as 51%. the last education of respondents is more S1 as much as 68%. Above the marital status of married more is married as much as 58%. A monthly income > 5,000,000 more shopping at Shopee as much as 25%. Purchases in the last 3 months shopped more Shopee which is 5 times.

4.1. Validity Test Results

4.1.1. Outer Loadings

This model explains how to determine the validity of this research:

Figure 2 Outer model results

4.1.2. Indicator Reliability

Outer loading ≥ 0.7 for theory testing and 0.5-0.7 for exploratory research (29).

Table 1 Outer loading results

	E-loyalty	E-satisfaction	E-trust	Web quality
Eloyalty_1	0,823			
Eloyalty_2	0,830			
Eloyalty_3	0,886			
Eloyalty_4	0,896			
Eloyalty_5	0,872			
Esatisfaction_1		0,904		
Esatisfaction_2		0,920		
Esatisfaction_3		0,929		
Esatisfaction_4		0,919		
Etrust_1			0,687	
Etrust_2			0,744	
Etrust_3			0,799	
Etrus_4			0,747	
Etrust_5			0,740	
Etrust_6			0,790	
Webquality_1				0,709
Webquality_2				0,708
Webquality_3				0,792
Webquality_4				0,778
Webquality_5				0,825
Webquality_6				0,822
Webquality_7				0,840
Webquality_8				0,835
Webquality_9				0,878
Webquality_10				0,849
Webquality_11				0,860

To assess the validity with the value of each variable obtained from the outer loading. If the outer loadings value reaches a value between 0.5-0.7 (29), the indicator is considered to meet the criteria. Based on the results of table 1, it is known that all variables in this study, namely e-loyalty, e-satisfaction, e-trust, and web quality all meet the criteria, namely valid.

4.1.3. Discriminant validity

The discriminant validity value is the cross loading factor value which aims to determine the discriminants in the research construct (30).

Below are the results of discriminant validity:

Table 2 Discriminant validity results

	E-loyalty	E-satisfaction	E-trust	Web Quality	Keterangan
E-loyalty	0,862				Valid
E-satisfaction	0,830	0,918			Valid
E-trust	0,605	0,695	0,738		Valid
Web quality	0,777	0,874	0,693	0,811	Valid

In table 2 above, the AVE value gets a greater result than the correlation of variables with other variables. So it is stated that all variables in this result are declared valid.

4.1.4. Internal consistency

The results of the composite reliability are as follows:

Table 3 Internal consistency results

Matriks	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
E-loyalty	0,913	0,935
E-satisfaction	0,938	0,955
E-trust	0,833	0,878
Web Quality	0,947	0,955

Composite reliability > 0.7 for theory testing and > 0.6 for exploratory research. Cronbach's alpha > 0.7 for theory testing and > 0.6 for exploratory research (29). Based on the results in table 3.10 above, the values for each variable have met the overall criteria. The composite reliability value has exceeded > 0.7. The Cronbach's alpha value has also exceeded > 0.7. It can be concluded that the overall construct of this study has a good reliability value, as seen by the fulfillment of all values > 0.7 in each assessment produced.

4.1.5. Convergent validity

The following are the results of convergent validity:

Table 4 Convergent validity results

Matriks	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
E-loyalty	0,743
E-satisfaction	0,843
E-trust	0,545
Web Quality	0,657

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is used to evaluate convergent validity. The AVE value must be more than 0.5 (29). There is table 3.11 AVE results can be stated that the e-trust construct has an AVE value of 0.545, which indicates adequate convergent validity. In addition, all other constructs have AVE values above 0.5, which also indicates that they meet the requirements for convergent validity.

4.1.6. R-Square

The coefficient of determination (R^2) in general the R^2 value ≥ 0.75 is good (29). The R-Square value from the results of this study can be used to measure the influence of external variables on the internal variables in this study.

Table 5 R square results

Variabel	R Square	R square adjusted
E-loyalty	0,700	0,691
E-satisfaction	0,780	0,775
E-trust	0,480	0,474

Based on the table above e-loyalty 0.700 means 70% is influenced by the observed factors, the remaining 30% is influenced by external factors. E-satisfaction of 0.780 means 78% is influenced by the observed factors, the remaining 22% is influenced by external factors. E-trust of 0.480 means e-trust influences the observed factors by 48%, the remaining 52% is influenced by external factors of this study that were observed.

4.1.7. F-square

After calculating the R-Square value, the next step is to calculate the outer value of the F-Square as follows:

Table 6 F-square Results

	E-loyalty	E-satisfaction	E-trust	Web quality
E-loyalty				
E-satisfaction	0,296			
E-trust	0,001	0,070		
Web quality	0,032	1,349	0,923	

There is an insignificant contribution of e-trust to the f-square of e-loyalty with a value of 0.001. The remaining variables e-satisfaction, e-loyalty, web quality are significant.

4.2. Direct effect

This hypothesis testing aims to determine the relationship between research variables. This is done by the bootstrapping method on the research model, then analyzing the t-statistic value and its significance level against the P-value in the Path coefficient table.

Table 7 The results of the path coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
E-satisfaction -> E-loyalty	0,635	0,608	0,118	5,384	0,000
E-Trust -> E-Loyalty	0,020	0,040	0,096	0,211	0,833
E-Trust -> E-Satisfaction	0,172	0,816	0,078	2,209	0,030
Web Quality -> E-loyalty	0,207	0,212	0,104	2,003	0,048
Web Quality -> E-Satisfaction	0,755	0,741	0,083	9,082	0,000
Web Quality -> E-Trust	0,693	0,699	0,069	10,047	0,000

Based on the results of the path coefficient in table 3.14 above, the results of the calculation of the direct influence test in this study from the t-statistic obtained with a total of >1.96 with a p-value of α : 5% (0.05). E-satisfaction has a significant positive effect on e-loyalty, that e-trust is not significant on e-loyalty, that e-trust has a significant positive effect on e-satisfaction, web quality has a significant positive effect on e-loyalty, web quality has a significant positive effect on e-satisfaction, web quality has a significant positive effect on e-trust.

4.3. Indirect effect

Models in management research are becoming increasingly complex, increasing the possibility of indirect impacts (i.e. indirect and total impacts) and the need to compare these impacts (31). The following are the specific indirect effects in this study:

Table 8 Specific indirect effects results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
E-trust -> E-satisfaction -> E-Loyalty	0,109	0,112	0,052	2,115	0,037
Web quality -> e-trust -> e-satisfaction	0,076	0,078	0,037	2,024	0,046
Web quality -> e-satisfaction -> e-loyalty	0,480	0,425	0,110	4,342	0,000
Web quality -> e-trust -> e-loyalty	0,014	0,029	0,067	0,208	0,836
Web quality -> e-trust -> e-satisfaction	0,119	0,130	0,056	2,117	0,037

It is known in table 8 that the indirect effects are as follows:

The effect of e-trust with e-satisfaction and then on e-loyalty shows the original value of the sample amount of 0.109, the sample mean is 0.112 with a standard deviation of 0.052. The t-statistic value is 2.115 with a positive value and p-values of 0.037. So it is said that e-trust has a positive effect on e-satisfaction through e-loyalty.

The influence of web quality on e-trust and then on e-satisfaction shows the original sample value of 0.076. The sample mean is 0.078 with a standard deviation of 0.037. The t-statistic value is 2.024 with a positive value and p-values of 0.046. So it is said that web quality has a positive effect on e-trust through e-satisfaction.

The influence of web quality on e-satisfaction and then on e-loyalty shows the original sample value of 0.480. The sample mean is 0.425 with a standard deviation of 0.110. The t-statistic value is 4.342 with a positive value and p-values of 0.000. So it is said that web quality has a positive effect on e-satisfaction through e-loyalty.

The influence of web quality with e-trust and then on e-loyalty shows the original sample value of 0.014. The sample mean is 0.029 with a standard deviation of 0.067. The t-statistic value is 0.208 with a value of less and p-values of 0.836. So it is said that web quality is not significant to e-trust through e-loyalty.

The influence of web quality on e-trust and then on e-satisfaction shows the t-statistic value is 2.117 with a positive value and at a p-value of 0.037. So it is said that web quality has a positive effect on e-trust through e-satisfaction.

4.4. Total effect

The total effect of a model also serves as input for importance performance map analysis (IPMA) and extends the standard PLS-SEM reporting of path coefficient estimates by adding a dimension to the analysis that considers the average of the latent variable score values (32).

The following are the results of the total effects in this study as follows:

Table 9 Results of Total Effects

	E-loyalty	E-satisfaction	E-trust	Web quality
E-loyalty				
E-satisfaction	0,635			
E-trust	0,129	0,172		
Web quality	0,777	0,874	0,693	

The following is an explanation of the values in the table above:

Web quality has a total effect on e-satisfaction with a value of 0.874 indicating a very strong positive correlation between web quality and e-satisfaction. The better the quality of the website, the higher the resulting e-satisfaction. The effect of web quality on e-satisfaction is not entirely direct, but there are other variables that mediate (intermediate) this relationship. However, even though there is mediation, the total effect remains very strong (0.874).

Web quality has a total effect on e-loyalty with a value of 0.777 indicating a strong positive correlation between web quality and e-loyalty. The better the quality of the website, the more likely customers are to be loyal. Web quality on e-loyalty is not entirely direct, but there are other variables that mediate (intermediate) this relationship. However, even though there are mediating factors, the total effect remains significant and strong (0.777).

Web quality has a total effect on e-trust with a value of 0.693 indicating a strong positive correlation between web quality and e-trust. The level of web quality is positively correlated with e-trust. There is no direct relationship between web quality and e-trust, on the contrary, there are other factors that function as intermediaries. The total effect remains strong (0.693).

E-satisfaction has a total effect on e-loyalty with a value of 0.635, indicating that there is a fairly strong positive correlation between e-satisfaction and e-loyalty. Although this number is not as strong as higher values (above 0.7 or 0.8), the value shows a significant positive correlation. This means that the higher the level of e-satisfaction, the higher the likelihood that customers will remain loyal. E-satisfaction and e-trust are not directly related, there are other factors that regulate this relationship. The total effect remains quite strong (0.635), even though there are mediating factors.

E-trust has a total effect on e-satisfaction with a value of 0.172 indicating a weak positive correlation between e-trust and e-satisfaction. E-trust is affected by e-satisfaction with a weak value. Customer trust in a company is important, but its impact on customer satisfaction is not significant. In other words, a number lower than 1 indicates a weak positive correlation between e-trust and e-satisfaction. The effect of e-trust on e-satisfaction is not entirely direct because there are other variables that mediate (intervene) this relationship. However, even though there are mediating factors, the total effect remains small (0.172).

E-trust has a total effect on e-loyalty with a value of 0.129 indicating a weak positive correlation between e-trust and e-loyalty with a value of 0.129, e-trust has a very weak effect on e-loyalty. Although there is a positive correlation, the relationship is very weak. This shows that, although there is a slight effect of customer trust on customer loyalty, the effect of e-trust on loyalty, e-trust is not entirely direct, but is mediated by other factors. Although there are mediating factors, the total effect remains weak (0.129).

The results of this study explain that website quality has a good effect on e-loyalty. This study supports the research of López and Varquez (17) and Alshurideh (12) that the same effect of web quality on e-loyalty is positive and significant. Website quality has a positive effect on e-trust. This study supports the research of Alshurideh (12) that the same effect of web quality on e-trust is positive and significant. Website quality has an effect on e-satisfaction. This study supports the research of Pandjaitan (21) and Giao, Vuong and Quan (1) that the effect of web quality on e-satisfaction is positive or significant. Website quality can increase shopee customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction refers to the level of customer happiness towards using products from the shopee company.

In this result, e-trust has no significant (negative) influence on e-loyalty. Arya S (11) are not supported by this study and López and Varquez (17) study shows that e-trust has a direct and significant relationship on e-loyalty. This study found that e-trust on e-loyalty is not significant or negative. So it is said that e-trust on e-loyalty is not enough to fulfill the trust

of customers who shop at Shopee. E-trust on Shopee is still considered less trusted in this study. E-loyalty in this study Shopee is still considered less loyal, which results in uncertainty for customers to return to shop at Shopee.

E-trust has a positive and significant effect on e-satisfaction on shopee. This study proves that e-trust has a positive but irrelevant effect on e-satisfaction (25). E-trust significantly affects e-satisfaction provides support for significant e-trust on e-satisfaction (9). These two studies have different results on e-trust on e-satisfaction (25). E-trust has a positive but insignificant effect on e-satisfaction, Ghane's previous study e-trust significantly affects e-satisfaction. In other words, there are differences between the two previous studies. But e-trust has a positive effect on e-satisfaction, the same as Ghane's research supports this study.

In this finding, e-satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on e-loyalty. According to previous research by Azli and Ghane (9) e-satisfaction is positively related to e-loyalty. This study proves that e-satisfaction, like e-trust, has a direct and immediate effect on e-loyalty. E-satisfaction has a positive effect on e-loyalty, the same as research by Azli and Ghane (9) which supports this study.

Web quality has no significant effect on e-loyalty through e-trust on the Shopee marketplace. Found that website quality as it is has a positive and significant effect on e-trust through e-loyalty, which has the most significant effect on e-trust (17). A research by Giao, Yuong and Quan (1) states that e-trust and e-satisfaction are mediating factors in the relationship between website and e-loyalty because lack of e-trust and e-satisfaction can be the main reason customers decide not to shop online or they may consider switching to another website. This study does not support research by López and Varquez (17) and and Giao, Yuong and Quan (1) which shows that web quality has an effect on e-trust through e-loyalty. This study shows that web quality does not have a significant effect on electronic trust (e-trust) through electronic loyalty (e-loyalty).

Web quality has a significant effect on e-loyalty through e-satisfaction on the Shopee marketplace. This study supports the research of Afsar and Nasiri (28) and Giao, Yuong and Quan (1) web quality on e-satisfaction through e-loyalty has a direct effect. The study shows that good web quality and high Shopee e-loyalty in the eyes of customers have a positive impact on increasing e-satisfaction on Shopee. Customer loyalty to Shopee tends to cause them to recommend this Shopee to people closest to customers.

5. Conclusion

This study can be concluded: (1) Website quality has a positive and significant effect on e-loyalty for Shopee marketplace users. Customers will be more likely to return to shop at Shopee because it is easy to use, has the latest information, and customers are satisfied. (2) The effect of website quality on e-trust for Shopee marketplace users is positive and significant. Believing that the quality of the website when shopping at Shopee is safe makes customers feel comfortable and not worried about shopping. (3) The effect of website quality on e-satisfaction for Shopee marketplace users is positive and significant. This satisfaction proves that shopping can provide a good customer experience to its customers in terms of ease of access, speed of response, transaction security, and quality of goods or services provided. (4) The effect of e-trust on e-loyalty with Shopee marketplace users is negative and insignificant. Consumers feel less confident that Shopee will fulfill its commitments. This can include product quality, delivery time promises, return policies, and good customer service. (5) The influence of e-trust on e-satisfaction of Shopee marketplace users is positive and significant. Shopee is trustworthy and provides services as expected, customers are satisfied and happy with Shopee. (6) The influence of e-satisfaction on e-loyalty on the influence of shopee marketplace customers is positive and significant. Customers feel very satisfied and happy with the services they receive on the shopee website, which encourages them to buy products on shopee again. (7) E-trust is unable to mediate the influence of web quality on e-loyalty. Users may pay more attention to other factors such as price, promotion, and delivery speed than web quality. Although the shopee website is of high quality, these factors may be more determinant of e-loyalty. (8) E-satisfaction is able to significantly mediate the influence of web quality on the e-loyalty of shopee marketplace users. Users feel very satisfied with the quality of shopee services, so they want to recommend it to people to use it, because customers are sure that the shopping experience at shopee will be satisfying.

There are several limitations of this study: (1) There are obstacles in finding respondents to fill out the questionnaire with the criteria in this study. (2) Constraints in selecting variables in this study. (3) This study uses e-trust and e-satisfaction as a link between web quality and e-loyalty if different mediators are included in the existing framework, the relationship may be stronger and more comprehensive.

Researchers suggest to companies: (1) The results of this study can be used as inspiration for the Shopee marketplace company to pay more attention to customer trust, including information that is important to its customers. By paying

more attention to the problems experienced by customers by providing the information needed by customers, Shopee can improve the quality of service and customer trust. (2) Shopee is expected to maintain and even increase customer satisfaction, because customers are happy with Shopee's online services so that customers remain loyal to buying from Shopee. Researchers suggest for further research: (1) It is hoped that subsequent researchers will consider including additional variables that have not been studied in this study. By including additional variables, it can provide a significant and in-depth contribution to the understanding of this Shopee research. (2) Efforts are made to increase the number of samples and respondents so that the results are better, more representative and accurate.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Giao HNK, Vuong BN, Quan TN. The influence of website quality on consumer's e-loyalty through the mediating role of e-trust and e-satisfaction: An evidence from online shopping in Vietnam. *Uncertain Supply Chain Manag.* 2020;8(2):351–70.
- [2] Pellicelli AC. Exploring e-Loyalty Antecedents in B2C e-Commerce Empirical results from Italian grocery retailers. 2022;(April).
- [3] Ibrahim A, Napian SDR, Firanisa A, Sartika, Sari RD, Audya M. The Effect of E-Commerce Application Service Quality of Customer Loyalty Using Customer Relationship Management Approach. 2020;172(Siconian 2019):680–7.
- [4] Anderson RE, Srinivasan SS. E-Satisfaction and E-Loyalty: A Contingency Framework. *Psychol Mark.* 2003;20(2):123–38.
- [5] Kusumawati A, Rahayu KS. The effect of experience quality on customer perceived value and customer satisfaction and its impact on customer loyalty. *TQM J.* 2020;32(6):1525–40.
- [6] Sreeram A. Factors affecting satisfaction and loyalty in online grocery shopping: an integrated model. 2017;9(2):107–32.
- [7] Chou S, Chen CW, Lin JY. Female online shoppers: Examining the mediating roles of e-satisfaction and e-trust on e-loyalty development. *Internet Res.* 2015;25(4):542–61.
- [8] Kim H, Niehm LS. The Impact of Website Quality on Information Quality, Value, and Loyalty Intentions in Apparel Retailing. *J Interact Mark [Internet].* 2009;23(3):221–33. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2009.04.009>
- [9] Azli N, Ghane S, Fathian M, Gholamian MR. Full Relationship among e- quality , and e-loyalty : The case of Iran e-banking. *J Theor Appl Inf Technol.* 2011;33(1):1–6.
- [10] Cyr D, Hassanein K, Head M, Ivanov A. The role of social presence in establishing loyalty in e-Service environments. 2007;19:43–56.
- [11] Arya S, Srivastava S. Effects of user ' s primary need on relationship between e-loyalty and its antecedents. *DECISION.* 2015;42(4):419–49.
- [12] Alshurideh MT, Al Kurdi B, Aburayya A, Al-Khayyal A, Alshurideh M. The Impact of Electronic Service Quality Dimensions on Customers' E-Shopping and E-Loyalty via the Impact of E-satisfaction and E-Trust: AQualitative Approach. *Int J Innov Creat Chang www.ijicc.net [Internet].* 2020;14(9):257–81. Available from: www.ijicc.net
- [13] Goutam D. Customer Loyalty Development In Online Shopping : An Integration Of E-Service Quality Model And The Commitment-Trust Theory. *School Of Management National Institute Of Technology Karnataka; 2020.*
- [14] Kaya B, Behravesh E, Abubakar AM, Kaya OS, Orús C. The Moderating Role of Website Familiarity in the Relationships Between e-Service Quality, e-Satisfaction and e-Loyalty. *J Internet Commer [Internet].* 2019;18(4):369–94. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332861.2019.1668658>
- [15] Ribbink D, Riel ACR Van, Liljander V, Streukens S. Comfort your online customer : quality , trust and loyalty on the internet. 2004;446–56.

- [16] Bulut ZA. Determinants of Repurchase Intention in Online Shopping: a Turkish Consumer ' s Perspective. 2015;6(10):55–63.
- [17] López-Miguens MJ, Vázquez EG. An integral model of e-loyalty from the consumer's perspective. *Comput Human Behav.* 2017;72:397–411.
- [18] Demir M, Karahanna E, Vannoy S, Mcknight DH, Choudhury V, Kacmar C. Developing and validating trust measures for e-commerce: An integrative typology. *Related papers Developing and Validating Trust Measures for e-Commerce: An Integrative Typology.* 2002;
- [19] Anser MK, Tabash MI, Nassani AA, Aldakhil AM, Yousaf Z. Toward the e-loyalty of digital library users: investigating the role of e-service quality and e-trust in digital economy. *Libr Hi Tech.* 2021;
- [20] Yu, W., Ramanathan, R. and Nath P. Northumbria Research Link (www.northumbria.ac.uk/nrl). 2017;51(September):1–51.
- [21] Pandjaitan DRH, S MM, Hadianto B. Website Quality, E-satisfaction, and E-loyalty of Users Based on The Virtual Distribution Channel. *J Distrib Sci.* 2021;19(7):113–21.
- [22] Chang HH, Chen SW. The impact of customer interface quality, satisfaction and switching costs on e-loyalty: Internet experience as a moderator. *Comput Human Behav.* 2008;24(6):2927–44.
- [23] Caruana A, Ewing MT. How corporate reputation, quality, and value influence online loyalty. *J Bus Res [Internet].* 2010;63(9–10):1103–10. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2009.04.030>
- [24] Schlosser AE, White TB, Lloyd SM. Converting Web Site Visitors into Buyers: How Web Site Investment and Online Purchase Intentions “ I. 2006;(May).
- [25] Juwaini A, Chidir G, Novitasari D, Iskandar J, Hutagalung D, Pramono T, et al. The role of customer e-trust, customer e-service quality and customer e-satisfaction on customer e-loyalty. *Int J Data Netw Sci.* 2022;6(2):477–86.
- [26] Ashiq R, Hussain A. Exploring the effects of e-service quality and e-trust on consumers' e-satisfaction and e-loyalty: insights from online shoppers in Pakistan. *J Electron Bus Digit Econ.* 2023;
- [27] Montoya-Weiss MM, Voss GB, Grewal D. Determinants of Online Channel Use and Overall Satisfaction with a Relational, Multichannel Service Provider. *J Acad Mark Sci.* 2003;31(4):448–58.
- [28] Afsar A, Nasiri Z. E-loyalty Model in e-Commerce. 2013;4(9):547–53.
- [29] Widarjono A. ANALISIS MULTIVARIAT TERAPAN (Dengan Program SPSS, AMOS, dan SMARTPLS). edisi kedua. Yogyakarta: UPP STIM YKPN; 2020.
- [30] Musyaffi ayatulloh michael, Khairunnisa H, Respati D kismayanti. konsep dasar structural equation model-partial least square (sem-pls) menggunakan smartpls. Tangerang Selatan: Pascal Books; 2022.
- [31] Streukens S, Leroi-Werelds S. Bootstrapping and PLS-SEM: A step-by-step guide to get more out of your bootstrap results. *Eur Manag J [Internet].* 2016;34(6):618–32. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2016.06.003>
- [32] Hair JF, Risher JJ, Sarstedt M, Ringle CM. When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *Eur Bus Rev.* 2019;31(1):2–24.